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Molecular Biomarkers in Prediction of Radiation-Induced Pneumonitis After Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy for Lung Cancer

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Stereotactic Body Radiotherapy (SBRT) has become the golden standard for treating early-stage, inoperable non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) due to its precision and high efficacy. However, radiation-induced pneumonitis (RP) can occur as a significant adverse effect that can negatively impact patient outcomes. The frequency of symptomatic RP in SBRT-treated patients varies widely, reported in the range of 9% to 28%. The incidence and severity of RP are influenced by various factors, including radiation dose/fractionation regimen, V20, V5, mean lung dose, tumor size and location, and previous pulmonary disease (i.e. interstitial lung disease-ILD). The identification of personalized biomarkers for predicting the likelihood of developing RP is essential for better risk stratification and personalized treatment planning. Krebs von den Lungen-6 (KL-6) and surfactant protein D (SP-D) are two biomarkers that made the focus of interest being identified as prognostic indicators for RP. They are associated with damaged alveolar type II cells suggesting treatment-related ILD and patient more susceptible to radiation. Elevated serum levels of these biomarkers prior to radiation are poor prognostic markers that correspond with increased incidence and severity of RP. Advances in identifying individual risk factors, such as the identification of prognostic biomarkers like KL-6 and SP-D, enhance the ability to predict and mitigate the risk of RP, ensuring that SBRT continues to be a viable and preferred option for patients with early-stage inoperable NSCLC.

Keywords: molecular biomarkers, stereotactic body radiotherapy, lung cancer, radiation pneumonitis

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